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Does Corporate Governance Improve Financial Performance? Empirical Evidence from Africa Listed Consumer Retailing Companies

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Abstract

The role of corporate governance (CEO duality, high concentration of ownership, diverse board membership, a sizable board, an independent audit committee, and regular board meetings) in boosting financial performance at firms is investigated. Over a period of 10 years, 49 consumer retailing companies listed on the West, East, and Southern African Stock Exchanges were subjected to a fixed effect model following a Hausman Specification Test for 2012-2021. There were four proxies for financial performance: two accounting metrics (Return on Assets and Return on Equity) and two market metrics (Tobin's Q and Market Capitalization). The findings show that having a larger board and a CEO duality is positively correlated with financial results. However, the results did not show any correlation between the frequency of audit committee meetings and improved financial results. Greater board and audit committee independence may be reevaluated for relevance to firm financial performance by regulators and policymakers.

Keywords: audit committee, board characteristics, corporate governance, financial performance, frequency of meetings, ownership concentration.

1. Introduction

There is poor financial performance on the part of corporations trading on the floors of Africa's Stock Exchanges (Ujunwa, 2012; Umar et al., 2021; Velnampy & Pratheepkanth, 2012; Yahaya et al., 2015; Yahaya & Ogwiji, 2021; Yahaya & Yusuf, 2020). The problem is deep and long; it calls for concern from corporate managers, owners, boards, scholars, regulators and policy-makers. This scenario may result in discouraging both local and foreign investments; thus, hampering the much needed economic growth for the continent. Also, empirical evidence linking corporate governance mechanisms to financial performance are few in the

continent, in terms of proxies used, models, period of coverage, research design and empirical findings. Thus, there is need to investigate further how various corporate governance measures can improve corporate financial performance in the continent. A strong corporate governance is seen in this paper as panacea to the poor firm financial performance.

Investment choices must be based on reliable and accurate financial data. However, some businesses engage in "window dressing," or the manipulation of financial data, to present an image of their finances that is less than honest. Consequently, the presence of independent auditors is crucial to gaining the confidence of investors and serving as a check on any potentially corrupt internal operations (Corplaw, 2014; Leung et al., 2014). An effective internal control structure relies heavily on the work of the audit committee (Nuryanah & Islam, 2011). It evaluates the company's financial statements and acts as an intermediary between the board of directors, management, and external and internal auditors to ensure open communication and accountability (Bhardwaj & Rao, 2015). There are provisions in the various countries Acts that encourage audit committees to have more autonomy.

There is a general consensus among investors that businesses gain an advantage when they voluntarily adopt corporate governance practices beyond those required by law (Aggarwal & Williamson, 2006). The success, growth, and longevity of any business can be traced back to the quality of its corporate governance, which must be firm, efficient, and transparent. The increasingly cutthroat nature of markets on a global scale have increased the importance of good corporate governance in all areas of business. Aware of this need, the various countries Corporate Matters Acts expanded the duties of audit committees. Their responsibilities now also include analyzing financial statements and weighing the merits of various investments and property.

This study provides an empirical analysis of the connection between audit committee independence and meeting frequency and firm performance. The study also examines the correlation between board composition (including the number of insiders) and company performance. There are two ways in which this research adds to the existing body of knowledge: To begin, the study has taken into account an additional measure of firm performance (market capitalization of a firm) in order to see how different corporate governance determinants (audit committee, duality, board size, composition, and promoter shareholding) affect a company's market performance. One way to determine a company's worth on the open market is to calculate its market capitalization, which is the market value multiplied by the current share price times the current number of outstanding shares. Because it did not involve any sort of accounting, it was deemed a non-manipulable variable and thus included as a supplementary metric. Second, the importance of the audit committee to a company's financial health was investigated in depth. In doing so, we followed the advice of Ameer et al. (2010) and Beasley et al. (2000), who suggested that the independence of the audit committee and the frequency with which it met contributed to the reduction of financial frauds in a firm and, by extension, improved the firm's financial performance.

Because accountants are tasked with determining whether a company's financial statements accurately portray the company's true position and value in terms of income, assets, and equity, the connection between audit committee and firm performance is of paramount importance. A strong audit committee is essential for any company that values its reputation for openness. The board of directors, which includes audit committee members, is in charge of developing plans to strengthen the company's financial position. Therefore, the board of directors and the CEO will be better able to draw effective strategies to improve the firm's performance if the audit committee presents a true picture of the financial statements to them (Bhardwaj & Rao, 2015). The audit committee is an important governance mechanism designed to ensure that a company produces relevant, adequate, and credible information that investors and independent observers can use to assess company performance (Sarkar, 2013). Several companies such as Enron Corporation, Global Crossing, WorldCom, Adelphia, and Tyco are just a few examples of international cases where investors were cheated through under financial performance. In many cases, financial records would not have revealed the poor performance until much later. Bhasin (2013) highlights the importance of an independent audit committee, claimed that weak independent directors and audit committee contributed to the poor financial performance. In order to maximize its effectiveness, Yunos et al. (2014) recommended holding audit committee meetings on a regular basis.

Though many studies have looked at the connection between corporate governance and financial performance (Mishra & Mohanty, 2014; Rodriguez-Fernandez et al., 2014; Velnampy, 2013), only a small number have focused on the function of audit committees. The agency theory proposed by Fama and Jensen (1983) dates back to the origins of the audit committee, which was established to promote board and committee autonomy and cut down on agency costs. Meetings of the audit committee and the people who make up the audit committee are two possible indicators of the committee's effectiveness, as proposed by Menon and Williams (1994). Two-thirds of the committee should consist of independent members, as per the various countries Companies Acts, and at least four meetings should be held annually. It was argued by Jemison and Oakley (1983) that an audit committee should consist entirely of independent directors. Since an audit committee comprised entirely of inside directors would never reveal the true picture of the firm's financial position to investors.

The enactment of Companies and Allied Matters Acts has made rules regarding the presence of an independent audit committee more stringent in order to curb poor financial performance. This study seeks to determine the impact of the role of corporate governance in firm performance. Following this introduction, the rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a literature review on corporate governance mechanisms and firm performance. The study's methods are outlined in Section 3. The analysis of the data is presented in Section 4, and the conclusions and recommendations are presented in Section 5.

2. Literature Review

The board of directors has a significant responsibility to increase shareholder value (Fama & Jensen, 1983). When shareholders buy into a company, they give the board this authority (Fama, 1980). When it comes to keeping tabs on how their money is being spent, however, shareholders often lack the means to do so (Grossman & Hart, 1980; Holmstrom, 1982). Financial performance of a firm, as measured by return on assets, return on equity, and Tobin's Q, has been found to be affected by the variables considered in this study: size of the board, board composition, CEO duality, ownership concentration (Ibrahim & Samad, 2014; Kiel & Nicholson 2003; Rhoades et al., 2001). However, little research has been conducted into the importance of corporate governance characteristics. This study fills this knowledge gap by examining the impact of corporate governance on financial performance.

2.1 Board Independence and Financial Performance

There has been a lot of research done to determine if board independence improves or hinders a company's financial performance. Independent directors were advocated by Brickley et al. (1994) and Fama and Jensen (1983) because they thought it would lead to more stringent monitoring of the board's activities and, in turn, better firm financial performance. A recent study found that companies with more independent board members had higher financial performance (Dharmadasa et al., 2014; Lin, 2011; Pahuja, 2011; Yahaya et al., 2015). Independent boards have been linked by Denis and Sarin (2017) to higher stock prices. Because of the potential impact on their professional reputation, independent directors may exert extra effort to ensure a project's success, which may explain these results (Eisenberg et al., 2018). In the event of a project failure, they stand to lose both credibility and money. However, some studies (Koerniadi & Tourani, 2012; Leung et al., 2014; Shan & McIver, 2011) argue that independent directors may not have sufficient information and knowledge about the firm, so there can be no positive association between the independence of directors and firm financial performance. We therefore propose that:

H₁: Board independence has no significant effect on financial performance.

2.2 Board Size and Financial Performance

Several studies have established that board size influences firm financial performance. Stakeholders would benefit from a larger board (De Oliveira Gondrige et al., 2012; Fauzi & Locke, 2012; Saibaba & Ansari, 2012; Ujunwa, 2012). The inability of smaller boards to make strategic changes was cited by Hambrick et al. (2008). This was attributed to the fact that such boards were less likely to thoroughly investigate and weigh all of the available options for expanding the company. On the other hand, numerous researchers favour smaller boards and are of the view that large boards lead to non-cooperation and waste of time in decision making as they suffer from social loafing. Thus, their knowledge and skills remain under-utilized (Dharmadasa et al., 2014; Drakos, & Bekiris, 2010; Jensen, 1993; Lin, 2011). (Dharmadasa et al., 2014; Drakos, & Bekiris, 2010; Jensen, 1993; Lin, 2011). We therefore propose that:

H₂: Board size has no significant influence on financial performance.

2.3 CEO Duality and Financial Performance

CEO duality, in which the same person holds both the CEO and the Chairman of the board positions, raises the question of whether or not this arrangement has an impact on a company's bottom line. The literature we have so far shows us that there are different ways to look at this. Critics of the CEO's dual role argue that having so much power concentrated in one person may not be in the company's best interest (Kaymak & Bektas, 2008; Lin, 2011; Ujunwa, 2012). CEO duality, according to Bliss (2011), can compromise the board's impartiality. In order to avoid disagreements and speed up decision making, researchers like Brickley et al. (1997) and Dahya et al. (1996) advocated for a CEO to play a dual role. There is no link between having a co-CEO and a company's success, according to several other studies (De Oliveira et al., 2012; Dharmadasa et al., 2014; Schmid & Zimmermann, 2008). We therefore propose that:

H₃: CEO duality has no significant impact on financial performance.

2.4 Ownership Concentration and Financial Performance

Concentration of ownership is a key internal corporate governance factor. The theory of agency offers justifications for and criticisms of greater promoter shareholding. Numerous studies on the subject have concluded that the monitoring capacity of a large promoter shareholding can lower agency costs between principal and agent (Anderson & Reeb, 2003; McDonald et al., 1998). Because of the high level of promoter shareholding, the free rider problem that arises from diffuse ownership can be avoided. Still, there are drawbacks associated with a large promoter shareholding. Increased agency cost between the majority and

minority shareholders is possible (Burkart et al., 2002; Faccio & Lang, 2002). The presence of promoters in a company's stockholding structure is generally viewed as a boon to financial performance. Since promoters have a vested interest in the company's continued success, their focus will inevitably be there (Chami, 2001; and James, 1999). The results of previous studies can be broken down into three groups: 1) promoter shareholding and firm value are unrelated (Demsetz and Villalonga, 2001); 2) shareholder profit increases with increasing ownership level (Anderson & Reeb, 2003; Andres, 2008; Haldar, & Rao, 2011; Kumar & Singh, 2013); and 3) there is a nonlinear relation between family ownership and the value of firm (Holderness et al., 1999; Dahya & McConnell, 2005). We therefore propose that:

H₄: Ownership concentration has no significant impact on financial performance.

2.5 Audit Committee Independence and Financial Performance

The independent directors of the audit committee can keep the bad behaviour of managers in check through a variety of monitoring processes, which is why the audit committee is seen as an important part of corporate governance. According to Cohen (2011), a vital component of an efficient audit committee is its ability to operate independently. In order to prevent managers from engaging in manipulative, self-serving behaviour, an independent audit committee may prove useful. Firms are mandated by corporate governance codes to establish audit committees and guarantee the committee's independence. Independent members of audit committees reduce the likelihood of fraud occurring at a company (Beasley, 2016). According to Bukit and Iskandar (2009), it was found that the presence of an independent audit committee reduced the frequency with which earnings were artificially inflated. Earnings management and audit committee independence were found to be inversely related by Abbott (2002). Authors (Arslan et al., 2014; Bouaziz & Triki, 2012; Nuryanah & Islam, 2011; Yasser et al., 2011) have noted that the presence of an independent audit committee is positively correlated with an increase in both the reliability of audit reports and the effectiveness of the firm. We therefore propose that:

H₅: Audit committee independence has no significant effect on financial performance.

2.6 Audit Committee Meetings and Financial Performance

According to Al-Mamun (2014), an effective way to mitigate agency costs and information asymmetry within a company is to hold regular audit committee meetings where relevant and timely information can be disseminated to investors. The prevalence of fraud in businesses might be reduced if they had audit committees that were both impartial and objective in their work (Yunos et al., 2014). Members of the committee would be able to examine the company's financial performance and standing objectively if they were unaffiliated with the business (Subrata Sarkar, 2013). According to research by DeZoort et al. (2002), companies with more frequent audit committee meetings are more likely to take measures to protect their investors' interests. Bryan (2004) looked into the suggestions made by the Blue Ribbon Committee (1999) to enhance the performance of corporate audit committees. He concluded that audit committees would improve financial reporting practices if they included more financially savvy and independently-minded board members who met regularly. When investigating whether the board relied on the audit committee as a tool to control managers, Menon and Williams (1994) looked at two characteristics of the audit committee (meeting frequency and independence) and found that both contributed to better monitoring of the firm, which in turn could lead to better performance. Several studies observing the relationship between audit committee meeting frequency and firm performance have given mixed results. Kyereboah-Coleman (2008) found that frequent audit committee meetings had a positive effect on market measures of firm performance, while Abdul and Haneem (2006) and Mohd Saleh et al. (2007) provided evidence that reducing the number of audit committee meetings improved the firm's financial performance. We therefore propose that:

H₆: Audit committee meetings have no significant impact on financial performance.

2.7 Firm Leverage and Financial Performance

Leverage measures how much of a company's debt is comprised of loans with long maturities. Although the capital structure of a firm has little bearing on its market value (the Modigliani-Miller framework), it does have a bearing on the performance of the firm if the agency cost of the firm is reduced due to increased debt (Jensen, 1986). Therefore, we have included leverage as a control in our analysis. Interestingly, high leverage led to lower return on assets of firms, but increased Tobin's Q, as found by Olokoyo (2013) and numerous other authors, including De Oliveira Gondrige et al. (2012), Fauzi and Locke (2012), Lama (2013), Zeitun and Gang Tian (2007). Because of this, it can be concluded that a firm's accounting performance suffers when its debt levels rise, while the market's perception of the firm's performance improves. The possibility exists that the over-leveraged state of some firms accounts for the discrepancy between Jensen (1986) and other authors' findings. We therefore propose that:

H₇: Firm financial leverage has no significant influence on financial performance.

2.8 Firm Listing Age and Financial Performance

Listing age is a measurement of the number of years that have passed since the company was listed. The connection between how long a company has been listed and how successful it has been is murky at best. When compared to startups, established businesses fare better thanks to the reputation they've built up over time (Mousa et al., 2012). However, due to their inherent rigidity and complacency, established businesses typically struggle to embrace innovative technologies (Anderson & Reeb, 2003). We have thus controlled for firm age to account for its impact on firm performance. We therefore propose that:

H₈: Firm listing age has no significant influence on financial performance.

3. Methodology

For the years 2012-2021, information was gathered from forty-nine (49) consumer retailing companies listed on West, East, and Southern African Stock Exchanges. All dependent and independent variables were winsorized at the 1% level to remove the impact of any outliers or unusual data. The information was analyzed by means of a fixed effect panel data regression model. The fixed effect estimation strategy was validated by the Hausman specification test. With the help of the serial correlation LM test, we analyzed the dependence of each cross-sectional sample over time and found that there was no correlation between the samples. In order to test for heteroskedasticity in the cross section residuals, the white test was performed using the Huber white coefficient covariance estimator on cross section data broken down by year. Based on the output, it appeared that the data was homoscedastic. Next, we estimated robust standard errors using white period standard error, which gave us reliable t statistics. The following regression model was used to achieve the objective of the study:

$$FP_{it} = P_0 + P_1 BC_{i,t} + P_2 BS_{i,t} + P_3 CEO_{i,t} + P_4 OC_{i,t} + P_5 ACIND_{i,t} + P_6 ACM_{i,t} + P_7 LEV_{i,t} + P_8 FAGE_{it} + u_{it}$$

Whereas:

Table 1

Variables and their definitions

i	Firm 1 to 49
t	year 1 to 10
FP _{it}	Financial performance for firm <u>i</u> at time <u>t</u> measured using ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q and M Cap as proxies
ROA	Return on Assets i.e. the ratio of total income and total assets
ROE	Return on Equity i.e. ratio of net income to shareholder's equity
Tobin's Q	Ratio of market value of firm to total assets
Market value of firm	Market value of equity + market value of debt
M Cap	Market Capitalization (Stock price * shares outstanding)
a _i	time invariant intercept for firm i.
BC	Board Composition i.e. number of independent directors on the board
BS	Board size i.e. total number of directors on the board
CEOD	CEOD i.e. whether the position of Chairman of the board and CEO is occupied by same person. 0 is given when there is no duality and 1 otherwise.
OC	Ownership concentration i.e. % shares owned by promoters
ACIND	% independent directors in the audit committee
ACM	number of meeting of audit committee in a year
LEV	ratio of debt to equity
FAGE	firm age from the year of incorporation
u	residual or disturbance term

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Furthermore, empirical analysis of the model was carried out to establish the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on firm financial performance. Specifically, these analyses indicate the influences of board independence, board size, CEO duality, ownership concentration, audit committee independence, audit committee meetings, financial leverage and firm listing age in improving financial performance of the firms. The analyses started with descriptive statistics, clearly showing the mean, median, maximum, minimum, standard deviation (volatility), skewness and kurtosis. These results are provided in Table 2.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2 displays the descriptive analysis results. According to the data in the table, most African businesses have ten directors on their board. One person holds the dual roles of CEO and Chairman of the Board in 37% of companies. promoters held 51% of the company's shares on average, and every board had at least five independent members. These findings are in agreement with Saibaba (2013). The high level of ownership by promoters has both positive and negative aspects. Owners' interest in the company's financial health ensures that agency costs are kept to a minimum, and vice versa. However, promoters may seek to limit the number of new investors in the company in order to advance their own agendas (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). The likelihood of fraud rises with this type of ownership, according to Loebbecke et al. (1989). Another interesting finding is that independent members of the audit committee make up more than 85% of the total (members who are in no way linked with the firm and other executive directors). In studies, it was discovered that companies typically hold 5 audit committee meetings per year. The average ROI was found to be 9%, while the ROI for their equity was 80%.

Table 2

Descriptive statistics

	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Skewness	Kurtosis
BC	5.09	5.00	10.00	1.00	1.80	0.39	2.94
BS	9.82	10.00	17.00	5.00	2.69	0.43	2.88
CEOD	0.37	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.48	0.55	1.30
OC	50.72	50.83	96.08	0.00	18.02	-0.02	3.13
LN_FAGE	3.53	3.50	4.94	1.79	0.61	-0.13	2.59
LN_LEV	1.30	1.26	2.30	-0.58	0.21	0.65	9.38
ACM	5.02	4.00	11.00	3.00	1.53	1.62	5.80
ACIND	85.09	100	100	0.00	17.79	-1.41	6.59
ROA	0.09	0.07	0.35	-0.15	0.07	0.75	4.33
LN_ROE	0.80	0.77	2.19	-1.00	0.18	2.42	32.28
LN_MCAP	9.84	9.67	14.56	3.07	1.68	0.32	3.05
LN_TOQ	0.38	0.28	3.04	-2.10	0.82	0.41	3.45

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

In order to determine the degree to which certain independent variables were correlated with one another, a correlation analysis was conducted. Non-correlation between the variables is essential for objectively interpreting the data. Table 02 makes it clear that there is little to no correlation between any of the variables. Number of independent directors was found to be correlated strongly (0.70) with board size. However, this correlation value is within reasonable bounds, so neither variable had to be discarded. The Variance Inflation Factor was used to conduct a robustness test, with the same outcomes being found. There was no evidence of multicollinearity in the data because no VIF value was higher than 8.

Table 3
Correlation matrix

	BS	BC	CEOD	OC	ACM	ACIND	LN_FAGE	LN_LEV
BS	1							
BC	0.73	1						
CEOD	0.06	0.08	1					
OC	-0.03	-	0.11	1				
		0.16						
ACM	0.26	0.14	0.06	-	1			
				0.09				
ACIND	0.10	0.36	0.06	-	0.07	1		
				0.14				
LN_FAGE	0.07	0.07	-0.07	-	0.07	-0.05	1	
				0.04				
LN_LEV	-0.04	0.00	-0.05	-	-	0.07	-0.05	1
				0.05	0.11			

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

Fixed effect panel data regression was used for the empirical investigation. Initially, factors besides audit committee make-up were included in the analysis of corporate governance mechanisms. Different models were used to examine the impact of corporate governance on each of the four performance measures (ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q, and market capitalization). The data on firm age, leverage, return on equity, Tobin's Q, and market capitalization were log transformed to reduce variance. The results were calculated at a 5%, 10%, and 1% level of significance. Finding a significant negative association between independence of board and firm performance as measured by return on assets, Tobin's Q, and market capitalization, the results show that African firms cannot advance when there are too many independent directors on the board (i.e. lesser the number of independent directors on the board, better the firm performance).

Finally, return on equity (ROE) was found to have no bearing on the autonomy of the board. This result agrees with those of Denis and Sarin (2017) as well as Ujunwa (2012). All measures of firm performance were found to be positively correlated with board size, but only Tobin's Q and market capitalization were found to have a positive and statistically significant correlation. The results from the other metrics were too vague to draw any firm conclusions. To sum up, we can conclude that larger boards do not improve the long-term effectiveness of African businesses as measured by conventional accounting metrics. Consistent with prior research (De Oliveira et al., 2012; Dharmadasa et al., 2014; Schmid & Zimmermann, 2008), we found that a company's leadership structure or a CEO holding a dual role is positively correlated to the company's bottom line. This means that the firm's optimal utilization of its assets and capital, as well as a number of other factors, are heavily influenced by a single person acting in both roles of CEO and Chairman of the board. The models explained well the variance of corporate governance variables on firm performance measures as the value of R square was more than 60% in all cases and the p value of F statistic was less than 5%.

Additional research was conducted to examine the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on firm performance, this time taking into account the qualities of the audit committee. Our findings did not find any improvement in the overall regression model, despite regulators' belief that an audit committee's presence, and more specifically a greater degree of independence, can decrease financial statement frauds and lead to an increase in firm performance. Based on ROE analysis, we can conclude that the degree of audit committee independence positively and significantly contributes to improving firm performance, whereas the presence of independent directors in the audit committee is found to have a positive but insignificant relationship with ROA. Both the Tobin's Q and a company's market cap are correlated negatively with their performance. While the correlation between market cap and Tobin's Q is weak, it is still there and has some importance. When there are more non-executive directors on the audit committee, it's possible that the company's assets will be undervalued. The result agrees with those of Bouaziz and Triki (2012). More independent directors on the audit committee improves the committee's ability to monitor, as shown by the results.

When measured by Tobin's Q and market capitalization, it was found that the frequency of audit committee meetings had a significant and positive effect on firm performance. Including audit committee traits modified the correlation between firm performance (ROA) and other corporate governance mechanisms. Board size and promoter shareholding were found to have a positive significant relation with return on assets after audit committee characteristics were included, while the relationship between leadership structure and ROA was found to be insignificant. The composition of boards has been significantly correlated negatively.

All measures of performance except Tobin's Q were inversely and significantly related to leverage. Consistent with the findings of Olokoyo (2013), these findings demonstrate that a high level of debt reduces the returns of firms. The correlation between firm age and Tobin's Q was identical. It would appear that younger companies are increasing their profits and stock value. Potential causes include their focus on expansion and adoption of cutting-edge technologies. As shown by the F statistic (p 0.000), the R square values of all models that accounted for audit committee characteristics were greater than 60%, indicating that the generated model is suitable for predicting financial performance of a firm and can also be used for the population.

Table 4
FEM Regression Results

Independent Variables	Model 1 (ROA)	Model 2 (ROE)	Model 3 (TOQ)	Model 4 (M Cap)	Model 5 (ROA)	Model 6 (ROE)	Model 7 (TOQ)	Model 8 (M Cap)
Intercept	0.000	0.000	0.441	0.494	0.000	0.000	0.400	0.490
BS	0.105 (1.620)	0.562 (0.579)	0.002** (3.044)	0.000*** (3.821)	0.095* (1.671)	0.470 (0.722)	0.600 (2.653)	0.001*** (3.398)
CEOD	0.045** (2.002)	0.006** (2.727)	0.072* (1.798)	0.008** (2.643)	0.322 (2.009)	0.005** (2.810)	0.082* (1.741)	0.011** (2.544)
BC	0.000*** (-4.741)	0.546 (-0.604)	0.013** (-2.488)	0.042** (-2.035)	0.000*** (-4.875)	0.218 (-1.231)	0.172 (-1.365)	0.119 (-1.560)
OC	0.301 (1.035)	0.010** (2.566)	0.854 (-0.184)	0.408 (-0.827)	0.045** (0.990)	0.012** (2.520)	0.903 (-0.121)	0.421 (-0.805)
ACIND	—	—	—	—	0.530 (0.628)	0.054* (1.928)	0.026** (-2.232)	0.642 (0.464)
ACM	—	—	—	—	0.812 (-0.237)	0.001*** (-3.482)	0.029** (2.188)	0.080* (1.753)
Ln_LEV	0.000*** (-5.604)	0.038** (-2.080)	0.211 (-1.251)	0.007** (-2.72)	0.000*** (-5.586)	0.036** (-2.101)	0.208 (-1.260)	0.006** (-2.756)
Ln_FAGE	0.016** (-2.416)	0.000*** (-4.050)	0.590 (-0.538)	0.000*** (4.358)	0.022** (-2.297)	0.000*** (-3.750)	0.553 (-0.593)	0.000*** (4.321)
Observations	2350	2350	2350	2350	2350	2350	2350	2350
R- squared	0.649	0.662	0.708	0.849	0.649	0.662	0.708	0.849
Prob (F-statistic)	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000

t statistics are in parentheses.

*** denote significance at 1%, ** denote significance at 5% and * denote significance at 10%.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study's findings provide further evidence that larger boards are associated with higher firm financial performance when measured by Tobin's Q and market capitalization. The findings are consistent with the findings of other studies (De Oliveira et al., 2012; Fauzi, & Locke, 2012; Saibaba & Ansari, 2012; Ujunwa, 2012). Also, the study's findings suggest that a larger number of directors on the board is associated with higher stock prices and greater investor confidence. Also, increasing the number of independent board directors would have a negative impact on the company's return on equity. Possible causes include independent directors' inability to boost profits due to a lack of relevant expertise. Some corporate governance mechanisms perform better when the audit committee is independent and meets frequently. Possible causes include the timely disclosure of accurate financial information to the board of directors and the prevention of fraudulent accounting practices.

In light of these findings, regulators should take note of the calls for greater autonomy for boards and audit committees. Despite the requirement in the Companies Acts (various countries) that at least four audit committee meetings be held annually, we found that the frequency of audit committee meetings had no effect on firm financial performance (ROA) and a negative significant effect on return on equity (ROE). Accordingly, more study is needed to ascertain the impact of audit committee meetings on the success of businesses. In addition, although a positive correlation between audit committee independence and return on equity (ROE) was discovered, this result alone cannot be used to draw the conclusion that audit committee independence has a substantial impact on firm performance; other measures of firm performance should also be considered.

This study has flaws, but it is just like every other one. Due to a lack of information about companies that did not keep their annual reports after the end of the fiscal year, only 49 companies were included in the analysis. In addition, the impact of corporate governance on firm financial performance is only examined for a subset of factors (board composition and size, CEO duality, ownership concentration, audit committee independence, and audit committee meeting frequency). It is possible that other factors, like board composition, institutional ownership, directors' tenure, auditors' turnover, audit committee members' expertise, etc., have an impact on a company's success.

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